

Modelling and Speed Control of Ground Mobile-Robot

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Abstract - This paper describes effective algorithm of modelling and speed control for differential wheeled Ground-Vehicle. Black-box modelling is performed to generate transfer functions of the left and right sides of the robot through system identification toolbox in Matlab. Proportional- Integral-Differential (PID) controller is designed for speed control of the vehicle to maintain desired stability criterions. The dynamic transfer functions of the left and right sides of the mobile robot are different so two PID controllers are designed. All of the testing and simulation results are verified in Matlab with detail explanations and discussions.

Keywords - Black-box modelling, System Identification, longitudinal stability control, PID, Matlab

I. INTRODUCTION

Wheeled mobile-robot has been increasing in recent years and many research developed for their possibility of the use in different outdoor environments such as transportation, surveillance, mining, and military missions and so on. The primary aim of this research is for the development of leader-follower multi robot system. This paper presents the modelling and speed control of the ground mobile-vehicle that will be an effective subsystem for the future high stabilized leader-follower system.

A. Background Research

A variety of research has been proposed for modelling and stability control for UGV (Unmanned Ground Vehicle). Research [1] provides the detail design and experiments of data collected in the system modelling in mathematical form of UGV system identification and control. Paper [2] describes the development of speed control for non-autonomous mobile vehicle for driving under difficult environment condition of surveillance aim at DORIS project. Reference [3] presents the modelling through system identification. This reference paper provides about black-box modelling intended for the electrical engineers without the knowledge on mechanical concepts. Research [4] provides the importance of low-level stability control in the development of the leader-following robotic application.

In this paper, longitudinal stability control is designed to maintain the desired stability performances. Black-box type modelling is performed through System Identification Toolbox in Matlab without the need to know mechanical structure of the motors.

B. Proposed system

The system of this paper is depicted in Fig. 1. The robot used is three wheeled vehicle. One is free wheel and the other two are dc motor drive. An optical encoder is implemented in each motor (left and right) to measure the speed of the wheel. The dynamic transfer functions of the two motors are estimated through system identification. PID (Proportional- Integral- Differential) based feedback stability control compensates robot's speed to maintain the desired performance. The speed sensed through encoder

would be compared with the set-point or the reference value, and error value is projected over PID controller and this process repeats until minimum error.

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of the System

C. Organization

This paper presents modelling and stability control for ground mobile-robot. It is organized as follows. Section II presents system architecture and main concepts that are required essential information to design this system. Section III describes the system design including control algorithm, identification and analysis of the controllers. Section VI presents testings and simulation results. Finally, Section V discusses the conclusions and future works.

II. MOBILE ROBOT

The hardware and software implemented in mobile robot used in this system described as follows:

Hardware: Arduino Uno
Two Tetrax DC motors
L298N Motor Driver
Battery

Programming Language: Arduino, Matlab

The robot has three wheels and the two are motor drive and one is free wheel. The two 12V Tetrax dc motors are implemented for left and right sides of the robot and which have the specifications of the gear ratio of 2:1 and maximum output speed of 76.1 RPM.

Fig. 2 Tetrax DC motor

The two motors of the robot are connected with L298 Dual H-Bridge motor driver which allows speed and direction of two DC motors at the same time. It can drive DC motors that have voltages between 5 and 35V, with a peak current up to 2A. Fig. 3 shows circuit diagram of L298 N motor driver connecting with the two motors in which 8-bit PWM signal from Arduino must be applied to pins of Enable 1 and Enable 2. Digital inputs (1 and 0)

from input1 and input 2 are to drive or change direction of the two motors which are connected to the output 1 and output 2 respectively.

Arduino Uno is implemented to drive the motors by applying PWM signal to the motor driver and to read sensors (encoders) data for the feedback loop. It is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P. The software used for this controller is Arduino Software (IDE).

Fig. 3 Circuit Diagram of L298N Connecting with Motors

The two wheel shaft optical encoder is to measure wheel speed. Optical encoder includes rotating or opaque disk and light sensor (photo transistor). Opaque disk has one or more circular tracks, with some arrangement of identical transparent windows (slits) in each track. The quadrature light detector measures the amount of light passed through the slotted disc and generates two quadrature output pulse signals, denoted by A and B.

Fig. 4 Quadrature Encoder Pulses

The encoders implemented in this research are two channels quadrature encoder, where one channel is shift by 90 degree each from the other. Fig. 4 shows the quadrature signal of incremental encoder. They have specifications of 5V supply voltage, 100 CPR (Count per Revolution), and 400 PPR (Pulse per Revolution). The encoder pulses are measured by Arduino microcontroller and converted to the wheel velocity.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

This section describes black-box modelling, open loop identification and PID controller for this research.

A. Modelling

Black-box modelling does not need to measure physical parameter of the system. It needs only experimental data (Input and Output data) in time. Black-box modelling is save time and easy because it does not need knowledge on mechanical structure and kinematic of the system. But, this type of modelling is less accuracy compared with mathematical modelling.

The flowchart in Fig. 5 describes the procedure of modelling in system identification. In this research, Modelling is performed at each side of the vehicle (left and right), so the two transfer functions are generated for left and right sides of the robot.

Fig. 5 Procedure of Modelling in System Identification

Data acquisition is the collecting of input and output data to find the dynamic models for left and right sides of the robot. To obtain best model of vehicle transfer function, data acquisition of the experimental data must be accurate so that the data must catch appropriate sampling interval, which is important factor in system identification. In this research, sampling time (T_s) of 0.1 second ($F_s=10\text{Hz}$) is used during data acquisition. This sampling frequency is high enough for UGV dynamic. The smaller sampling time creates more accurate system modelling but limitation must be noticed. The sampling frequency must not be less than the twice of system dynamic frequency ($F_s \geq 2F_{\max}$). Moreover, this experimental data must be changed due to the different environment such as rough or smooth floor and also at the condition of low power battery. Data acquisition of this research is in the smooth floor.

In data acquisition, the input data to the two sides of the robot is 8-bit PWM values and the output data is the speed measurement from the encoder. Pulses measure from the encoders are counted and converted to the rad/s by Eq. (1).

$$\text{Velocity, } \omega \text{ (rad/s)} = \frac{\frac{\text{Encoder Pulses} \times 60 \text{ sec}}{\text{Pulses} \text{ revolution}}}{\text{Fixed time interval (sec)}} \times \frac{2\pi}{60} \quad (1)$$

According to the Eq. (1), the mobile vehicle can move approximately maximum speed of 3.4 rad/s at maximum voltage of 12V or the maximum PWM pulse value of 255.

After the data acquisition, input and output data for each motors are imported to system identification toolbox. Fig. 6 shows the input and output data plots of the left and right sides.

(a)

Fig. 6 Output (rad/s) and Input (PWM) Data Logging of Robot (a) Left Side (b) Right Side

The next step is to generate transfer functions in different orders. Among them, second order with no zero and two poles was chosen for both left and right motors with best fits of 77.54% and 80.17% respectively shown in Fig. 7 (a) and (b).

Fig. 7 Transfer Function Estimation in System Identification Toolbox (a) Left side (b) Right side

After generating transfer functions, model validation was performed, which is the process of comparing the output of simulated transfer function and real system measured data output. In this system, model validation is performed different input and output data to the system identification toolbox again and compared with the simulated output of transfer function. After validation, the second order with no zero and two poles structure is the most convenient for both sides.

Fig. 8 Model Validation at System Identification Toolbox (a) Left side (b) Right side

Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) are the chosen transfer functions of left and right sides of vehicle.

$$\frac{\omega}{V} = \frac{2.148}{s^2 + 31.77s + 156.8} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\omega}{V} = \frac{2.296}{s^2 + 41.45s + 170.8} \quad (3)$$

B. Open loop Analysis

According to the open loop system shown in the block diagram of Fig. 9, step response plots for left and right sides' transfer functions are described in Fig. 9 in which $G(s)$ is the system dynamic model of left or right side. Both the input set-point and output are the unit of rad/s.

Fig. 9 Block Diagram of Open Loop system

Both motors achieve one half of the desired output i.e. at the input of 1 rad/s, the output is near 0.45 rad/s as can be seen in the response plots shown in Fig. 10.

And also, the desired specified stability criteria are specified as shown in Table. 1. The regarding of stability criteria is to reach and remain close to the desired reference value in the minimum time possible and the minimum overshoot above the desired value.

Fig. 10 Open Loop Step Response (a) Left side (b) Right side

As can be seen in step response plots, both left and right motors does not satisfied desired specifications and so the controller must developed to compensate this problem.

TABLE I
DESIRED PERFORMANCE SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Symbol (Unit)	Desired Performance
Settling Time	T_s (s)	<0.5s
Maximum Percent overshoot	M_p (%)	<2%
Peak Time	T_p (s)	<0.8s
Rise Time	T_r (s)	<0.2s

By root locus analysis, for both dc motor models, all of the poles are located at left hand side and so the systems are stable. PID controller is sufficient and discuss about it in Section III .C.

C. PID Controller

In this system, PID controller was designed for longitudinal stability control based on identified system model. The desired criteria were described in the previous article. In this section, PID controller design to obtain this desired stability performances. In Controller's design, the performance of different controller P (Proportional), PI (Proportional-Integral), and PID (Proportional-Integral-Differential) for both manual and auto tuning are analysed.

A proportional controller (P) consists of only a constant gain (K_p). The output of P controller is the constant multiple of the error (input signal-current state). Derivative controller (D) adds a differential gain (K_d). Derivative controller is useful in the systems of high frequency noise. But, in practice, a pure D controller is not used. Integral (I) controller is implemented by integrating the error in the system. The integral term considers the history of the error (summation of errors), or how long and how far the measured process variable or system state has been from the set-point over time. Fig. 11 shows the block diagram of PID controller.

Fig. 11 Control Block of PID Controller

The continuous PID controller equation is shown in Eq. (5).

$$C(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s \quad (5)$$

Table 2 [5] described the effects of parameters (K_p , K_i , and K_d) in PID controller on the response characteristics.

TABLE II
EFFECTS OF PARAMETERS IN PID CONTROLLER

Parameter	Rise Time (T_r)	Maximum Overshoot (M_p)	Settling Time (T_s)	Steady State Error (E_{ss})
K_p	Decrease	Increase	Small Change	Decrease
K_i	Decrease	Increase	Increase	Eliminate
K_d	Minor Change	Decrease	Decrease	No effect

IV. TEST AND SIMULATION RESULTS

The first step in system design is data acquisition of input and output data to generate transfer function. Fig. 12 shows data logging of input and output data on smooth floor. These data are stored in SD card's memory and is imported to the system identification toolbox.

Fig. 12 Input and Output Data Acquisition at Smooth Floor

In PID controller design, firstly, manual Proportional (P) controller was tried. Increasing proportional gain (K_p) has the effect of reducing rise time. The open loop model output is smaller than desired speed as discussed previous article. So the system is needed to increase K_p . But the greater the K_p , the higher the maximum overshoot. It is not

convenient the desired Percent Overshoot criterion of less than 2%.

Then Proportional-Integral Controller (PI) was tried and also high percent overshoot at high value of K_i . So, K_i decreases to reduce percent overshoot, but settling time increases again. To reduce settling time, the system is needed to combine with differential gain K_d .

So, Proportional -Integral -Differential controller (PID) is the best controller for this system. Both auto and manual PID tuning are performed and the simulation plots are described in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 Closed Loop Step Response Simulations with Different Controllers (a) Left side of mobile robot (b) Right side of mobile robot

The comparisons of the simulation of closed loop response's characteristics with different controllers for the left motor are shown in Table 3.

TABLE III
COMPARISONS OF CLOSED LOOP CHARACTERISTICS (LEFT MOTOR)

Controller	PID (Manual)	PID (Auto)	P (Manual)	PI (Manual)
K_p	6	4.341	700	10
K_i	30	35.334	0	50
K_d	0.09	0.0884	0	0
Rise Time (sec)	0.1333	0.1444	0.005	0.0645
Settling Time (sec)	0.2145	0.5099	0.2452	0.3259
Maximum Percent Overshoot (%)	0	7.5080	79.5953	12.8588
Peak Time (sec)	0.6434	0.3091	0.0143	0.1366
Steady State Error	0	0	0	0

The closed loop response characteristics with the different controllers of right side of the robot are described in Table 4.

TABLE IV
COMPARISONS OF CLOSED LOOP CHARACTERISTICS (RIGHT MOTOR)

Controller	PID (Manual)	PID (Auto)	P (Manual)	PI (Manual)
K_p	9.5	3.836	500	10
K_i	38.5	28.0175	0	20
K_d	0.15	0.0519	0	0
Rise Time (sec)	0.1154	0.1844	0.0059	0.0958
Settling Time (sec)	0.2008	0.6686	0.1841	1.0733
Maximum Percent Overshoot (%)	0	7.3434	71.0526	0
Peak Time (sec)	0.6674	0.4025	0.0164	2.3622
Steady State Error	0	0	0	0

As conclusion of the PID control simulation, all of the results shown in Fig. 13, Table 3, and Table 4 are performance comparisons for different PID controllers and among them, PID (Manual Tuning) is the best for both left and right sides which the most satisfactory the desired performance specifications described in Table 1.

Fig. 14 shows the simulation result of multiple set-points tracking for PID manual tuning, in which both input set-point and output are unit of rad/s.

Fig. 14 Simulation of Multiple Set- Point Tracking (a) Step Input (b) Ramp Input (c) Sinusoidal Input

V. CONCLUSIONS

This proposed system presents black-box typed system modelling and the longitudinal stability control for the grounded mobile robot. In this paper, linearized black-box modelling using system identification and PID controller design to compensate for desired performance are also described. In PID controller design, different controller types (P, PI, and PID) are discussed and analysed their

performance. All of the simulation results are verified with comparisons and discussions.

The current research is focus for high effective leader follower multi robot system with good stability performance for the future work. After implementing this system (Longitudinal stability control), Lateral stability control will also be added. The proposed model is linearized second order model so it would also be interesting to design with non-linear adaptive controls such as fuzzy-PID control for the parameter changes at different environment conditions. Moreover, the studies on sensitivities should be performed by integrating different error sources such as measuring noise, internal disturbances and so on. Most common mobile robot system based on the differential drive model i.e. two powered wheeled are used for both driving and changing direction as the same as this system. Omnidirectional mobile robot system in which both driving and changing are performed by the front steering is more accurate the leader-follower approach. So, front steering mobile robot system should be a future research.

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